

THREE-DIMENSIONAL MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THICK GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Three-dimensional material characterization of thick composites are investigated. The emphasis of this study is the matrix dominated behavior associated with transverse to the fiber direction. Therefore, the y- and z-direction tensile, compressive and shear properties are examined in detail with testing methods. Transverse shear testing methods for thick composites are evaluated and investigate strengths as well as moduli in 3-dimension.

INTRODUCTION

Thick composite laminate is of great interest as the application of composite is considered for primary structures. Failure analysis for thick composite requires the knowledge of stiffness and strength properties in three dimension, specially through-thickness properties. Most literatures on composite material characterization have dealt with plane properties for thin composites. Transverse shear properties in yz-plane are essential for the three-dimensional failure analysis of thick composites and the onset of delamination. Recently, three-dimensional moduli of thick composites[1-2] and mechanical behavior of woven fiber composites[3] were reported. However, three-dimensional strength properties of thick composites are not available in the literature. They assume the same value of shear strength, Q , in yz-plane as that of in-plane shear strength, S , when the onset of delamination is analyzed[4]. Measurements of shear strength in yz-plane(through-thickness) for the transverse-isotropic composites is not simple as the case of in-plane shear testing. Transverse shear properties in yz-plane are essential for the three-dimensional failure analysis of thick composites and the onset of delamination.

The objective of this paper is to carry out three-dimensional material characterization of thick composites. The emphasis of this study is the matrix dominated behavior associated with transverse to the fiber direction. Therefore, the y- and z-direction tensile, compressive and shear properties will be examined in detail with testing methods. Transverse shear testing methods for thick composites are evaluated and investigate strengths as well as moduli in three-dimension.

MATERIAL AND TESTING

Thick unidirectional graphite/epoxy laminate of 200 ply (T300/1043C) were fabricated using an autoclave process and examined by C-scan technique to confirm the acceptability as test specimens. After inspection, various sizes and shapes of specimens were cut from the laminate. As stated earlier, the emphasis of experiments is given to the matrix dominated behavior associated with transverse to the fiber direction. Therefore, tensile, compressive, and

shear properties in y and z direction were examined in detail. Transverse shear test methods for thick composites were evaluated and strength as well as moduli in three dimension were measured.

Measurements of all the moduli and strengths in longitudinal and transverse to the fiber direction for the in-plane properties is well defined. For the three-dimensional properties of thick composite laminate some more independent experiments should be carried out as shown in Fig. 1. However, the measurement of shear strength in y - z plane is not simple because transverse tensile strength is lower than shear strength. Evaluation of in-plane shear test methods for composite material is well established [5]. However, the popular shear test methods such as rail shear method, $[\pm 45]_s$ off-axis method, and $[10]$ off-axis method are not suitable for the measurement of shear strength in the y - z plane. Recently, the evaluation of asymmetric four-point bend method (AFPB) specimen and Iosipescu shear specimen were reported for thick-wall composites [6].

Fig. 1. Independent experiments for 3-D properties in thick laminates.

Fig. 2. Failure modes of asymmetric four point bend specimens.

In this study, several methods of transverse shear test such as AFPB, circular cylindrical rod test, and short beam test were examined for thick composites. AFPB specimens in the y - z plane do not show the true shear failure due to low transverse tensile strength property as shown in Fig. 2. Also, this undesirable tensile failure makes it difficult to use the circular cylindrical rod specimen by torsion test for shear strength measurement in y - z plane, although shear modulus can be determined [7]. A short beam specimen can not be used to measure transverse shear strength due to high aspect ratio of the thickness to span. The natural choice of shear strength testing in y - z plane of thick composite is the modified slotted notch specimen to induce true shear failure in the y - z plane. The specimen geometry for slotted specimen is shown in Fig. 3. Compression loading with side supports should be applied to prevent a transverse tensile failure at the notch as illustrated in Fig. 4. Finite element

stress analysis was carried out to investigate the specimen configuration of the slotted notch specimen for different notch lengths and thickness. Finite element model as shown in Figure 5 was constructed with 336 elements and 1077 nodal numbers using SAP6 isoparametric elements.

Shear strength properties of graphite/epoxy in x-y plane, x-z plane, and y-z plane with the different thickness of specimens are given in Table 3. Shear strength properties by the modified slotted notch specimen are influenced by the specimen thickness and applied loading conditions. In case of thin specimens the value of shear strength is lower than that in case of thick ones. This discrepancy of thin specimens comes from the undesired state of stresses at the notch as shown in Figure 6. Thin specimen shows somewhat high stress concentration near the edge. Therefore, all the specimens keep to be thick and under compressive loading as the specimen in y-z plane. The shear specimen in y-z plane for measurement of Q should be under compressive loading only due to low transverse tensile strength property as stated earlier. Table 1 and Table 2 show moduli and strength properties of unidirectional thick graphite/epoxy (T300/1043C). It should be noted that shear strength in y-z plane, Q is appreciably greater than those in x-y and x-z plane. As expected, thick composite properties showed same properties in y and z direction.

Fig.3. Specimen geometry for slotted shear specimen.

Fig.4. Various failure modes for slotted shear specimen.

Table 1. Engineering Constants of Unidirectional Thick Graphite/epoxy.

E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	E_z (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	G_{xz} (GPa)	G_{yz} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	ν_{xz}	ν_{yz}
124	8.96	9.0	5.1	5.1	2.9	0.31	0.02	0.55

E_x = Longitudinal Modulus in X-direction. G_{xy} = Shear Modulus in X-Y plane.
 E_y = Longitudinal Modulus in Y-direction. G_{xz} = Shear Modulus in X-Z plane.
 E_z = Longitudinal Modulus in Z-direction. G_{yz} = Shear Modulus in Y-Z plane.

Table 2. Strength of Unidirectional Thick Graphite/Epoxy in Mpa.

X	X'	Y	Y'	Z	Z'	S	R	Q
1234	1234	72.9	258	69.7	258	71.4	72.5	113

X, X' = Logitudinal Tensile, Compressive Strength.
 Y, Y' = Transverse Tensile, Compressive Strength.
 S = Shear Strength in X-Y plane.
 R = Shear Strength in X-Z plane.
 Q = Shear Strength in Y-Z plane.

Table 3. Shear Strength Properties of Graphite/Epoxy (T300/1034C).

Fiber volume : 67.2 % No. of plies : 200 (1 in. thick)

	d (mm)	w (mm)	t (mm)	strength		load
				(MPa)	(ksi)	
S	9.68	23	3.34	39.6	5.75	T
	9.68	23	3.34	53.5	7.77	C
	10.3	19	10.0	62.8	9.11	T
	10.3	19	10.0	80.	11.62	C
R	9.77	18	3.35	48.1	6.97	T
	9.77	18	3.35	75.5	10.96	C
	10.78	17.5	10.36	64	9.21	T
	10.8	17.5	10.29	81	11.77	C
Q	9.3	17.9	10.08	113	16.39	C

Note : S = shear strength in x-y plane
 R = shear strength in x-z plane
 Q = shear strength in y-z plane

T = tension
 C = compression

Fig.5. Finite element model for slotted shear specimen.

Fig.6. Shear stress distributions of thin & thick laminates.

CONCLUSION

Three-dimensional material characterization was carried out for thick composite laminate and testing methods for transverse shear strength were examined. A modified slotted notch specimen was proposed for the testing method of transverse shear strength. Moduli and strengths in transverse to the fiber direction can be treated as same. However, transverse shear strength turned out to be greater than in-plane shear strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was partially supported by Korean Ministry of Science and Technology. The authors also acknowledge the support of Mr. J. Camping of University of Dayton Research Institute for testing of specimens.

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